

ANALYZING DIFFICULTIES OF HUFİ STUDENTS TOWARD LISTENING COMPREHENSION

Ngo Thi Ngoc Hanh

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

Email: Bachtrunghanh9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to discover the issues that students encounter in studying listening skill. The expressive strategy was utilized to analyze and find out the best solution. The article uses the qualitative research method that bases on 100 students. The group of students in this study is second-year students English department of Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry. Information was accumulated by implies of surveys and interviews. The result uncovers that listening comprehension is exceptionally boring and troublesome for students majoring in English. Three fundamental components affecting students' listening comprehension are materials, listeners' factor, physical setting. At that point the analyst recommended a few conceivable ways in trust to illuminate the issues such as improving listening materials, activating students 'vocabulary, giving students chances to communicate with native speakers to correct pronunciation by themselves, giving students variety of accents while practicing in the lab, giving them some strategies in listening, and motivating students. This study may be a helpful suggestion for lecturers.

Keywords: Students' difficulties, listening comprehension, listening skill, students, teachers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Listening has an vital part both in lifestyle and in scholastic settings because it is important to individuals to support successful communication. Emphasizing the significance of listening skill, Anderson and Lynch (2003) expressed that listening skill is as vital as talking ability since individuals cannot communicate face-to-face unless both sorts of abilities are developed together. Listening skill is additionally basic for learning purposes since through listening in understudies get information and pick up encounters (Wallace, Stariha & Walberg, 2004). At Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry (in the future shortened as HUFİ), albeit all English-students began to study 3 listening courses in one and a half year with all total 90 periods, some of them didn't have the proficient listening ability. That prompts flounder in end of the year tests and convey wastefully. Numerous students grumbled that they have experienced issues in listening writings on account of they absence of jargon to comprehend the writings, the marterials are too hard to even consider following, and some goal factors. In this article, the analyst wanted to dissect the serious issues of second-year English majored college understudy of HUFİ so as to discover the best sollution to make listening exercises progressively successful and charming.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Most individuals think that being able to compose and talk in a foreign language infers that they know the language; be that as it may, on the off chance that they don't have the capable listening skill, it isn't conceivable to communicate successfully. That's, listening is the elemental in language learning, and over 50% of the time that students spend working in a foreign language will be devoted to listening (Nunan, 1998).

Rost (1994) claimed that listening is vital in dialect classroom as follows:

1. Tuning in is imperative within the dialect classroom since it gives input for the learner. Without understanding input at the correct level, any learning simply cannot start.
2. Talked dialect gives a means of interaction for the learner. Because learners must associate to attain understanding. Get to speakers of the language is basic. Additionally, learners' disappointment to get it the language they listen is a force, not a deterrent to interaction and learning.
3. Authentic spoken dialect presents a challenge for the learner to understand language as local speakers really utilize it.

In truth, tuning in may be a complex mental handle that incorporate acknowledgment, very troublesome errand for dialect learners. When tuning in to a outside language, numerous dialect learners confront challenges. In organize to help understudies advance their tuning in capacity, dialect instructors ought to get it students' tuning in troubles in comprehending talked writings, and taught compelling tuning in methodologies to assist understudies enlighten their tuning in challenges.

3 METHODOLOGY

The participants of this study are 100 second-year English major students who attended the school year 2019-2020 at Faculty of Foreign Language at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry. The study was conducted after the group of students had finished two listening skill courses entitled "Listening 1" and "Listening 2". The two courses of listening skill last for 60 in-class periods and 120 self-study periods, in which the students are required to listen some kinds of tasks.

The writer collected data by a list of questions and interview directly. All the questions were done when students were on the third week of the first semester of second-year students English Faculty of HUFU. The questions were answered in their classrooms in the breaktime.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION (CAN BE SEPERATED)

4.1 In-class English listening difficulties

This study involves statistical methods used in order to analyze the data obtained from 100 second-year English major students. The levels of in-class listening difficulties is indicated on a four-point rating scale ranging from "Strongly agree" valued as 1, "Agree" valued as 2, "Disagree" valued as 3, "Strongly disagree" valued as 4.

Table 1. Students's reponses to In-class English Listening Difficulties scale

Item No	Items	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Disagree (3)	Strongly disagree (4)
1	I spend much time on studying Listening.	11%	19%	38%	35%
2	I find that Listening skill is exciting.	10%	13%	36%	41%
3	I feel confident when doing Listening skill tasks .	12%	14%	34%	39%
4	I often practise Listening skill at home.	14%	12%	38%	36%
5	I always listen well although recording is in poor quality.	13%	15%	35%	37%
6	I find it easy when the speakers speak with a variety accents	9%	11%	38%	42%
7	I can follow when the speakers speak too fast.	8%	7%	43%	42%
8	I always keep listening when I think about the meaning of new words.	12%	9%	36%	43%
9	I can understand all although the speaker doesn't pause long enough.	8%	11%	39%	42%
10	I find it normal to understand the meaning of the spoken text without seeing the speaker's body language.	16%	13%	37%	34%

To explain the item number 9 in the table above “I can understand all although the speaker doesn't pause long enough”. It is evident for most language learners and instructors that a slower discourse speed would facilitate beginner learners' tuning in comprehension (Griffiths, 1990; Zhao, 1997). Blau (1990) concluded that reduce the input speed is one of the compelling technics that helps comprehension for second language learners.

There are distinctive levels of students in a classrom, the better students can tune in well and keep all the data in the mind. It could be a huge prolem for the lower others to tune in more than three munites long tuning in at that point completing the exercises. Tuning in brief writings encourage tuning in comprehension and diminish boredome, in any case, they can help learners concentration alive. In case of long texts, they are not simple to keep all information in intellect, exceptional listening ability. Another reason make tuning in text difficult is the speed. On the off chance that the speaker speaks faster than normal listener may have troubles to catch target word. Underwood

states that on the opposite of reading comprehension the listener cannot control speed of the speaker and this cause the most prominent trouble with tuning in comprehension (Underwood, 1989, p. 16).

Possibly within the big classrooms understudies who sit on the back row may not tune in the recordings as well as understudies as who sit in front. Understudies who like sitting by the windows also impacts by the noise that come from outside, especially, understudies very often hear the big sound of the planes taking off or landing at HUFU. The classromm with over 50 understudies also get difficulties for teacher to mangage all the activities or to get feedback from understudies. Indeed we are living 21st century which is that age of innovation still there are a few classrooms do not have computer, smart board, interactive media frameworks and so on. The quality of sound framework also influences understanding of tuning in.

Mendelson (1994) claimed that numerous sorts of highlighted discourse would result in a critical lessening in comprehension. Goss (1982) pointed out that usually ESL/EFL listeners are utilized to “their teacher’s accent or to the standard variety of British or American English”. In this case the instructors ought to familiarize the understudies both British and American complement, It is an unending talk about that what is the standard English? A few says the Britist English is spoken all over the world by India, Australia, Chinese, Turkish and so on. Students’s inspiration is one of the vital components that influence tuning in comprehension. It canbe troublesome for students keeping up the concentration in a remote dialect learning classrom. In tuning in comprehension, indeed the littlest stop in consideration may significantly ruin comprehension when students discover the subject of the turing in content curiously, comprehending would be simpler. For all that, understudies discover tuning in exceptionally boring indeed in the event that they are curious about the subject since it it needs a huge amount of exertion in organize to not miss the meaning. .Body dialect could be a portion of communication that exceptionally few really think about however it makes up most of what we utilize to communicate and is common much more exact a judge of meaning than are the words we utilize. That’s the reason a few students discover difficulties when tuning in without seeing the speaker’s body language.

Table 2. Sudents’s level of in-class Listening difficulties

Opinions	Average Percentages	Difficulty Level
Strongly agree and Agree (Values 1 and 2)	From 19% to 29%	Low
Strongly disagree and Disagree (Values 3 and 4)	From 71% to 81%	High

The result of the discriptive analysis shown in table 1 indicates that students get big problems with listening skill by various difficulties in classes. The troulbes are from the learners and objective factors.

4.2 Difficulties toward the tasks

The second questionnaire surveys what kinds of tasks in classes. The data were analyzed by computing the percentages of students’ responses on 5 common tasks in the textbooks.

Table 3. In-class listening tasks

Task No.	Task types	Percentage (%)				
		Very easy (1)	Easy (2)	Normal (3)	Very difficult (4)	Difficult (5)
1	Gap- filling	25%	29%	20%	12%	14%
2	True/ False	24%	26%	22%	15%	13%
3	Multiple choice	27%	23%	15%	18%	17%
4	Matching	23%	25%	17%	16%	19%
5	Sentence completion	11%	15%	12%	33%	29%
6	Answer the questions	9%	12%	15%	34%	30%

Table 2 reveals that the highest percentage of students reported that they felt easy with the tasks (1), (2), (3), and (4), from 65% to 74% of students do these tasks more easily than the others. We can realize that the types of the tasks are also an important to the learners, they feel easily with simple tasks and get problems with the tasks outputting detail information. On the other hand, materials are one of the difficulties of students in listening comprehension.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

To sum up, the findings of the Listening difficulties show that students have various kinds of difficulties in classes, the three main factors influencing students' listening are listening materials, listeners's factor, physical setting.

Clearly, tuning in comprehension has solid impact to the entire preparing handle of the students, tuning in comprehension requires the learners have sufficient lexicon, laguage structure, great suppliers, and procedure in tuning in. Studenrs of HUF1 are confroning all of them, these troulbes are enormous deterrents that they must overcome.

The teachers play an imperative part in instructing Listening ability for students. Teaching listening strategies to the understudies is uncommonly accomodating (Goh, 2000). But it isn't adequate unless the teachers raise students' lexicon, grammar, and phonology knowledge. Listening involves hearing, transforming, retaining, collecting and recovering information (Grunkemeyer, 1992). Besides, teacher ought to redesign the tasks that are appropriate for the levels of students in classrooms in order to motivate students' concentration. A modern lap is nescessary for practising listening. These days, language labs aren't the stockpiles of cassette tapes, CD players and microphones that some of us experienced a decade ago. Now they're computer rooms that are powered by state-of-the-art software designed to give students a unique and customizable learning experience—otherwise known as technology integration. They allow shy and self-conscious students a chance to practice their English in privacy. Students are more likely to pay attention when working with a program that's communicating specifically to them. The learning content can babanced to suit each student's individual needs. Students' listening and speaking skills can be tested more efficiently.

This study attempts to investigate the perception of the second-year English major students at HUFU of the English listening comprehension role in the process of language learning as well as the components that influence their listening comprehension. The research analyzed a few difficulties in listening comprehension moreover recommended a few proposals both students and teacher. The author trust that this study will be valuable for both students and teachers.

REFERENCE

- [1] Anderson, A. & Lynch, T. (2003). *Listening*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- [2] Blau, E.K. (1990). The effect of syntax, speed and pauses on listening comprehension. *TESOL Quarterly*, 24(4), 746–753
- [3] Carroll, J. B. (1977). *On learning from being told* In M. C. Wittrock (Ed.), *Learning and instruction* (2nd ed., pp.496-512). Cambridge; Berkeley, CA: McCutchan.
- [4] Griffiths, R. (1990). Speech rate and NNS comprehension: A preliminary study in timebenefit analysis. *Language Learning*, 40(3), 311–336.
- [5] Goh, C. C. M. (2000). A cognitive perspective on language learners' listening comprehension problems. *System*, 28(1), 55-75.
- [6] Goss, B (1982). *Listening as information processing* .*Communication Quarterly*, 30 , 304-307.
- [7] Grunkemeyer, F. (1992). Add two cups of flour and one cup of salt. *Texas Child care* 21,(4), 25. Mendelson, D. J. (1994). *Learning to listen*. USA: Dominie Press
- [8] Nunan, D. (1998). *Approaches to teaching listening in language classroom*. In proceedings of the 1997 Korean TESOL Conference. Taejon, Korea: KOTESOL.
- [9] Rost, M. (1994). *Introducing listening*. London: Penguin books
- [10] Underwood, M. (1989). *Teaching listening*. London: Longman.
- [11] Wallece, T., Stariha, W. E. & Walberg, H. J. (2004). *Teaching speaking, listening and writing*. France: Typhon.
- [12] Zhao, Y. (1997). The effects of listener's control of speech rate on second language comprehension. *Applied Linguistics*, 18(1), 49–68.